

Multi-objective quality metric for optimizing compilers

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Abstract

To obtain fast-executing computer code, optimizing compilers are used. The resulting code and the compilation process itself have several characteristics. The most important of them is the resulting code execution time, but the compilation time or the code size are also important for compiler users and should be minimized.

The research goal of this paper is to provide a tool that allows to explicitly control compilation characteristics and allow smooth tuning between all of them. That is, the idea is to construct a mathematical multi-objective criterion, or a compilation quality functional, for comparing two compilers using a test suite.

We show that the problem of choosing such a criterion for an arbitrary number of compilation characteristics has an exact solution that follows from user's evident expectations. The key findings are: (i) the functional must be multiplicative in its components, not additive; and (ii) it must be evaluated on the entire compilation task as a whole, not as a sum of independent per-procedure optima. We prove that an additive per-procedure functional does not reach the Pareto border for the whole task, while our multiplicative functional does.

As an example of constructed compilation quality functional application we illustrate its minimum points used for a posteriori selection of the optimizing sequences.

Keywords: compilation quality functional, multi-objective optimization, Pareto optimality, execution time, compile time, code size, scale invariance, compiler autotuning.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The performance of modern computers largely depends on the quality of the executable code optimization and scheduling, performed by various optimizing compilers in accordance with processor architecture features. During the compilation process some sequence of transformations is applied to the intermediate representation (IR) of the program. For some transformations [1], one can unambiguously determine the most effective parameters and triggering condition. However, for a significant part of the transformations, certain heuristic settings are used [2] [3] [4]. They allow to estimate the need and to specify the most promising method of their application to the code. Ideally, the transformation settings should be selected in such a way that it is applied optimally in each context. However, this is not always achievable, since even for the same executable code, the most effective way of planning can differ in the case of different execution scenario of the optimized program. Therefore, in the process of compiler development, the tuning of heuristical and statistical parameters of various optimizing transformations is performed statistically on some representative training suite of applications (most

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likely CPU benchmarks). And usually applications' execution times are combined in a single value to simplify the estimation of compiler quality with certain parameters set.

In addition to execution time, the compilation time is also explicitly or implicitly required to be taken into account. In the case of dynamic compilation, it is almost as important as the execution time. For a standalone compilation, the importance of compile time is less significant, but it should still be controlled, as some algorithms for code analysis and optimizations (e.g., peephole, def-use graph construction, pointer analysis) have quadratic computational complexity of $O(N^2)$ where N is the size of the intermediate representation being optimized. At the same time, a significant part of the transformations that increase the instruction level parallelism or allow to simplify some execution branches perform duplication of different parts of the code [5]. This leads to a significant increase of IR size and working time of subsequent optimizations. It should also be mentioned that higher compilation time would not always lead to a faster program execution time and could even lead to its slowdown. For example, most optimizations present in O3 (but not in O2) optimization level in gcc compiler noticeably increase the size of the code, which itself may cause processor pipeline stalls due to code cache misses [6]. As a result, most optimizations need limits in terms of code size boosting, and the most aggressive ones are only performed if compiler is invoked with the corresponding optimizing flag.

In recent years, machine learning techniques have emerged as a powerful alternative to hand-crafted heuristics. Approaches range from direct performance prediction [7] to reinforcement learning frameworks that treat optimization selection as a sequential decision problem [8], and program embeddings that capture syntactic and semantic properties of intermediate representation [9]. The GRACE framework [10] demonstrates that contrastive learning combined with evolutionary search can achieve significant code size reductions (over 10%) with tuning overhead under one second per program. Similarly, POSET-RL [11] applies reinforcement learning specifically to phase ordering for simultaneous optimization of code size and execution time.

As one can see, the development and configuration of each transformation and the entire optimization sequence is a balance between the execution time of the resulting code, the compilation time and the size of the code. This problem was repeatedly solved in the scientific literature. In [12] and [13] authors consider both the runtime speed and the size of the compiled code. The problem of mainly code-size directed compilation was considered in [14]. In [15] authors investigate the question of constructing the minimum optimization sequences, which allow obtaining the maximum execution speed for each procedure. On the test package for the gcc compiler the authors demonstrated the compilation time acceleration by an average of 2 times without loss in performance. But for such an acceleration of compilation in a certain sense an unlimited number of optimizing sequences was used. Thus, for each procedure an individual sequence of optimizing transformations was constructed. In other studies, some limits to the considered code are applied. For example, when constructing iterative compilers, the cold procedures [16] [17] are cleared. For some optimizations information about the profile of sections within the procedure is used [18] [19].

1.2 The problem: multi-objective quality criterion construction

The balance between several compilation characteristics is carried out by the developers of the compilers rather intuitively. Our goal here is to find some single numerical criterion, or a multi-objective scalarization [20], that allows developers to:

- adjust triggering conditions and parameters for single optimizations
- coordinate parameters adjustment for multiple optimizations
- make the metric that works for the whole weighted set of procedures for all the tasks in the pack

The main purpose of the wanted quality criterion in general is to compare several compilers. In case of compiler in the process of development, the criterion may be applied to incremental changes in certain optimizations design, as well as to the changes in the sequence of optimizations, or even to higher level changes in the compiler behavior, as we will see later in this paper.

Criterion can be useful for both a posteriori and a priori decisions on optimization behaviour. Parameters tuning can be performed using statistics of compilation characteristics and optimized applications execution, that is, a posteriori. The example presented in this paper is also a posteriori choice. In this case we actually compare all compilers with different compilation sequences assignment for procedures in a test suite.

In some studies a multi-objective criterion is already applied for a priori tuning. For example, such criterion for one application was used to tune the transformation of code substitution (inline) [21] or to solve the machine learning problem of a priori choice of the optimization sequence [22].

While existing ML-based approaches have shown impressive results on individual optimization tasks, they typically focus on a single objective (e.g., execution time or code size) or require application-specific tuning. The survey by Bachiri et al. [23] highlights that independent optimization of neural architecture and compiler passes often yields suboptimal results, motivating the need for joint optimization frameworks. Recent work on design space exploration [24] and evolutionary tuning [25] further demonstrates that multi-objective considerations are becoming central to compiler autotuning. However, a principled mathematical formulation of a multi-objective quality metric that works across arbitrary numbers of characteristics and procedures remains an open problem — which is exactly the gap our work addresses.

To construct the criterion required for the above tasks, it is necessary to determine what ratio between several characteristics is perceived as the most effective choice. That is, how much extra time the user is willing to spend on compilation to speed up execution by 1%. Or how much he agrees to increase the size of the code to speed up execution by 1%. And this perception must be reflected in the form of a function of characteristics. In this paper we want to answer a question:

What quality criterion would best match the user's expectations from the compilation process?

1.3 Our Results

The presented work solves the problem of an exact mathematical formulation of the compilation quality criterion which takes in account both execution and compilation time. Unlike recent ML-driven frameworks such as GRACE [10] or POSET-RL [11], which require training on program embeddings and per-task adaptation, our approach provides a closed-form mathematical solution derived from first principles. This makes it applicable both a posteriori (for evaluating existing compilers) and a priori (for guiding optimization decisions without costly retraining).

The user expectations from compilation process are represented in the form of rigorous constraints and requirements. On their basis, a number of statements about the compilation quality function are proved. In Section 2, different methods for comparison of the execution times of an applications package are described and analysed. Section 3 is devoted to multi-criteria optimization of compilation. Examples constructed in 3.1 illustrate the difference between finding Pareto optimum for individual procedures and for applications consisting of several procedures. In 3.2 it is explained how to make a transition from Pareto optimum to a functional minimum. In Section 3.3, we prove a number of statements which allow to define the exact form of the compilation quality function as a function of criteria. Statements in Section 3.4 illustrate Pareto minima points that are attainable as the minima of the compilation quality functionals.

Proposed study is mainly theoretical. However, in Section 4 we provide an example of application of the constructed functional to a posteriori compilation sequences selection for procedures in a suite.

2 Execution time of applications set

First, we consider comparing only the execution time of a certain applications set, where each application consists of a set of procedures. There are several aggregated metrics which are used to summarize overall performance over a benchmark suite for different performance metrics [26] [27]. Here we explain our choice of geometric average for applications' execution time aggregation. In addition, we focus on formulation the aggregated metric in terms of individual procedures, as it allow estimating the overall quality of compilation when applying different compilation strategies to different procedures of one application.

Definition. Let L be the space of all possible *optimization lines*, or optimization sequences with some regulation values set for each transformation in it. And suppose that $l^* : P \rightarrow L$ is a mapping that aligns any procedure an optimization line to compile it with. In the case of tuning only one optimization, the considered lines represent the same optimization sequence and differ only in corresponding optimization heuristics.

The simplest execution time quality criteria of an optimization line l^* for application pack is:

1) Comparison of the total execution time of all applications, that is, the sum of all procedures execution times.

Let $\text{exe}(p_i, l^*(p_i))$ be the procedure p_i execution time when using optimization line $l^*(p_i)$. Then the required functional has the following form

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \sum_i \text{exe}(p_i, l^*(p_i)) \quad (1)$$

As a result of minimizing the functional (1), the minimal execution time of the entire package will be received. However, applications with short execution time can lose a lot in performance along with the simultaneous performance boost of a long one within the constant functional value. Therefore, in order to balance application weights, a functional with normalization could be used:

2) Comparison of weighted applications' execution times sum.

Let $\text{exe}(p_i, l^*(p_i))$ be the execution time of procedure p_i after compilation with a sequence $l^*(p_i)$. The application weight is $w_k = \sum_{k_i} \text{exe}(p_{k_i}, l_{\text{start}}^*)$, where k_i are the procedures indexes for application number k , l_{start}^* - initial optimization line. Then the functional weighted by the execution times becomes:

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \sum_k \left(\frac{\sum_{k_i} \text{exe}(p_{k_i}, l^*(p_{k_i}))}{w_k} \right) \quad (2)$$

Note: The minimum of the functional 2 depends on the optimization line which was used to calculate weights. In this case, at the starting point $F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = k$.

The disadvantage of taking into account the weighted (2) and unweighted (1) sums of applications' execution times is that their slowdown becomes more significant than their acceleration. Thus, for an arithmetic mean, the acceleration of one application by a factor of 2 simultaneously with the slowdown of another by 1.5 is not considered beneficial. As a result, the optimum depends on the starting point, and one initially efficiently compiled application may not allow to the speedup the rest.

More independent from the starting quality of compilation functional is geometric mean of applications' execution times:

3) The geometric mean of applications' execution times is:

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \sqrt[K]{\prod_{ki} \left(\sum_{ki} \text{exe}(p_{ki}, l^*(p_{ki})) \right)} \quad (3)$$

where K — is the number of applications in a suite.

Note. The situation, in which a functional of the form Equation(3) reflects the quality of the choice, is quite typical. It requires for the decisions to be made for individual parts of the process. While for the consumer, it is important to minimize the sum of criteria value of a subset. A simple life example is shipping goods. The path in this case is divided into several segments, for each of which the delivery method or the order of shipping goods is chosen. In this case, only the total shipping time is important to the consumer. Using the same example, it is easy to formulate a multi-criteria problem of simultaneous minimization of the shipping time and its cost.

3 MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPILATION PROCESS

3.1 Pareto border for procedures and for applications

Lets now formalize the problem of minimizing not only the execution time of the procedures, but also the compilation time or the size of the resulting code. Simultaneous minimization of several characteristics is a multi-criteria optimization problem.

Definition 1. . *The problem of multi-criteria minimization is a problem of the form:*

$$f(x) = (f_1(x), \dots, f_k(x)) \rightarrow \min, x \in X, f(x) : X \rightarrow R^K, K \geq 2$$

Since, in the general case, there is no solution for all objective functions, instead of it, Pareto minimums are searched [28]. That is $x \in X$, such that there doesn't exist $x' \in X$, so that $f_i(x) \geq f_i(x') \forall i = 1 \dots k$ and $f_i(x) > f_i(x')$ at least for one i .

It will be shown in this paper that the multi-criteria optimization problem for compilation process could be solved by minimizing a single quality functional. Furthermore, we show that such functional for compilation and execution times could be represented only as a function of a certain form.

The goal of balancing compilation and execution time is to find some good points on the Pareto-minima boundary. In the described above cases, like choosing the hottest parts of the code, some balance is provided separately for each procedure. However, for a user, the Pareto boundary for the whole application and the entire compilation and execution process is of more interest. The essential difference between these requirements is shown in Figure 1 which illustrates different variations of procedures compilation for application 175.vpr from spec2000 CPU benchmark.

As a set of optimization lines, we used the Elbrus sequences of optimizations for O2 level, for O3 level, and two sequences constructed from O3 sequence with the flags and parameters for: cache optimizations, loop splittings, software pipelining, interchange, nesting, superbblocking, guess prefetch, list prefetching, maximum nodes sizes and scalar run time memory disambiguation. The flags and parameters for the last two lines were selected such that in addition to O2 and O3 lines they provide the highest performance increase of spec2000 benchmark suites.

Point $Proc_Min(Comp * Exe^7)$ shows that the minimization of independent procedures' characteristics functions doesn't provide whole application Pareto optimum. That is, in the case of multi-criteria optimization problem, a functional is needed not only to measure the

Figure 1: Pareto border for compilation and execution times for a set of optimizing lines.

The figure illustrates different compilation results for application 175.vpr of spec2000 benchmark suite. Points "O2 line", "O3 line", "line 3" and "line 4" stand for using the indicated optimization line for all procedures in the application. "Combined procedures pareto optimums" are the total compilation and execution times of the application when using for each procedure one of optimization sequences corresponding with its Pareto boundary. "Whole application Pareto optimums" are calculated for the whole application execution and compilation times. "Interesting point" is the optimization lines assignment point that we want to reach as a multi-objective optimization result. Point $Proc_Min(Comp * Exe^7)$ illustrates minimizing a function $comp(p) * exe(p)^7$ of compile and execution times for each procedure p independently.

Table 1: Compilation and execution times of procedures 1 and 2 when optimizing lines 1 and 2.

Procedure	Exe line 1	Exe line 2	Comp line 1	Comp line 2
Procedure 1	500	800	60	40
Procedure 2	400	500	60	40

Table 2: Optimizing line selection in case of a general constraint: selection of the minimum total execution time with the total compile time limited by the value Comp = 100.

Both Procedures	Line 1/line 1	Line 1/ line 2	Line 2/ line 1	Line 2/ line 2	Best Choice
Exe time	900	1000	1200	1300	1000
Comp	120	100	100	80	100

compilation difference for a suite which contains a set of applications, but even to tune the compilation of only one application.

In other words, the minimum of the functional

$$l_{\min}^* = \min_{l^*: P \rightarrow L} F(l^*(p_1) \dots l^*(p_n))$$

cannot be represented as

$$l^* = \left(\min_{l \in L} (F_1(l)), \dots \min_{l \in L} (F_n(l)) \right)$$

Example 1. In Table 1 and Table 2 an example of the optimization lines assignment dependence is constructed. For a given limit on compilation time it is impossible to use the best line in terms of execution time for both procedures. So a joint problem has to be solved.

Designation: $f_i(l^*(p_1) \dots l^*(p_n))$ - numerical compilation characteristics for the entire set of assignments

3.2 Scalarizing a multi-objective optimization problem

Let us now scalarize [20] [29] the multi-objective optimization problem of compilation. Which means that instead of the multi-objective optimization problem

$$f(x) = (f_1(x), \dots, f_k(x)) \rightarrow \min, x \in L^n, f(x) : X \rightarrow R^k,$$

we want to formulate a single-objective one

$$F(x) \rightarrow \min,$$

where $F(x)$ is a certain multi-parameter function

$F(f_1(x), \dots, f_k(x))$, or to a multi-criterial quality functional

$$F(l^*(p_1) \dots l^*(p_n)).$$

Since with the constant compilation time, the constructed function F should choose the compilation line that affords the fastest code, and since the same should be fulfilled in the case of constant execution time, F should be a strictly monotonic increasing function. The following lemma establishes that minima of such functions are reached in Pareto minima points. Further, this statement will be used to accurately construct a functional for evaluating the compilation quality.

Lemma 1. If a multi-criteria quality functional is a monotonic strictly increasing function of several characteristics, then its minimum is attained at the Pareto minimum point for these characteristics.

Note: The order relation for two points from R^k is determined only in the case when the order of all their corresponding coordinates is the same. Therefore, only for these points the monotonicity condition of the functional will be satisfied.

Proof. Let F be a monotonically increasing functional with respect to f_i and let x_0 be the found minimum point, that is, $F(f_1(x_0), \dots, f_k(x_0)) = \min(F(f_1, \dots, f_k))$.

Assume that there exists a point x_1 , that violates Pareto optimality for x_0 , that is, $\forall i : f_i(x_1) \leq f_i(x_0)$ and $\exists j : f_j(x_1) < f_j(x_0)$.

Because F — is a monotonically increasing function and $f_1(x_1) \leq f_1(x_0)$, then

$F(f_1(x_1), \dots, f_k(x_1)) \leq F(f_1(x_0), \dots, f_k(x_1))$, similarly, for all other characteristics except j . Since the value of the j -th characteristic for x_0 is higher than the value for x_1 , that is, $f_j(x_1) < f_j(x_0)$, then $F(f_1(x_1), \dots, f_k(x_1)) < F(f_1(x_0), \dots, f_k(x_0))$.

That is, the value of F in x_1 is less than the value of F in x_0 . Since we have got a contradiction with the fact that x_0 is the minimum of the functional F , the assumption is wrong. □

The structure of such a functional defines the optimal ratio of its arguments. It should be noted that the selection of this ratio depends on the problem being solved.

Example 2. *If the code performance is of decisive importance, but it is required to speed up the compilation time, then the functional may look like:*

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \frac{\sum_{ki} exe(p_{ki}, l^*(p_{ki}))}{(\sum_{ki} comp(p_{ki}, l^*(p_{ki}))+1)}$$

In the above example, the step of the first summand is always greater than the second one, so the value of the functional will always be less for the faster executing code.

Example 3. *For dynamic compilation or JIT (Just in Time), the compilation and execution times have the same weight, so the functional has the form:*

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \frac{\sum_{ki} exe(p_{ki}, l^*(p_{ki}))}{\sum_{ki} comp(p_{ki}, l^*(p_{ki}))} \quad (4)$$

3.3 The theorem on the functions that preserve order on scaling

To clarify the structure of the functional for static compilation, we introduce an additional user requirement. Suppose that the compiled task will be executed not one, but two times, that is, the execution time of each procedure will increase by 2 times. It is likely to expect that the lines chosen for the procedures remain the same.

In other words, we require minimum point preservation for coordinates scaling. That is, $\forall X \subset \mathbb{R}_+^k, \forall \alpha > 0, \forall j \in \overline{1, k}$, and X_j^α constructed from X multiplying all coordinates number j by α , from $F(x_1, \dots, x_k) = \min_{x \in X} F(x)$ follows:

$$F(x_1, \dots, \alpha \cdot x_j, \dots, x_k) = \min_{x \in X_j^\alpha} F(x) \quad (5)$$

Note. Let F be defined everywhere on \mathbb{R}_+^k . Condition (5) is equivalent to a more convenient condition of points order preservation for coordinates scaling in terms of functional meaning:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x_1 = \langle x_{11}, \dots, x_{1k} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}_+^k, x_2 = \langle x_{21}, \dots, x_{2k} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}_+^k \\ \text{from } F(x_1) \leq F(x_2) \text{ it follows that } \forall \alpha > 0, \forall j \in \overline{1, k} : \\ F(x_{11}, \dots, \alpha x_{1j}, \dots, x_{1k}) \leq F(x_{21}, \dots, \alpha x_{2j}, \dots, x_{2k}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In this section, we describe all possible scalarizations of multi-objective minimization problem which preserve points order for coordinates scaling. Lemma 2 denotes a class of functions fulfilling this condition. In theorem 1 we prove that denoted class contains all satisfying condition (6) functions. Lemma 3 establishes that to find all minima of denoted functions it is sufficient to consider a smaller class.

Lemma 2. *Let $f(x, y)$ be a monotonically increasing (monotonically decreasing) function in two variables defined everywhere on \mathbb{R}_+^k , representable in the form $f(x, y) = g(x^k \cdot y^j)$, then*

- 1) $g(x)$ - monotonically increasing (monotonically decreasing) function of one parameter
- 2) $f(x, y)$ satisfies the condition (6) of the points order preservation on scaling

Proof. For definiteness, let $f(x, y)$ be a monotone increasing function.

1) Suppose that $x_1 \leq x_2$, then $f\left(1, x_1^{\left(\frac{1}{j}\right)}\right) \leq f\left(1, x_2^{\left(\frac{1}{j}\right)}\right)$, that is, $\exists x_1, x_2 : g(x_1) > g(x_2), x_1 < x_2$.

2) We now consider $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 : f(x_1, y_1) \leq f(x_2, y_2)$. Then $g\left(x_1^k \cdot y_1^j\right) \leq g\left(x_2^k \cdot y_2^j\right)$ and, consequently, from 1), $x_1^k \cdot y_1^j \leq x_2^k \cdot y_2^j$. At the same time $f(a \cdot x_1, b \cdot y_1) = g\left(a \cdot b \cdot x_1^k \cdot y_1^j\right)$, $f(a \cdot x_2, b \cdot y_2) = g\left(a \cdot b \cdot x_2^k \cdot y_2^j\right)$. And because for positive a, b from $x_1^k \cdot y_1^j \leq x_2^k \cdot y_2^j$ follows $a \cdot b \cdot x_1^k \cdot y_1^j \leq a \cdot b \cdot x_2^k \cdot y_2^j$, then $f(a \cdot x_1, b \cdot y_1) \leq f(a \cdot x_2, b \cdot y_2)$ \square

Note: It could be proved similarly that the properties in 2 are valid for functions of any number of variables.

Theorem 1. *Let $f(x, y)$ be a strictly monotone continuous function of two variables defined everywhere on \mathbb{R}_+^k and satisfying (5) on the whole domain of definition. Then it is representable in the form:*

$$f(x, y) = g(x^q \cdot y), \quad q \in \mathbb{R}, \quad q > 0$$

Proof. 1) Let us show that through any point (x_0, y_0) pass the equipotential curve of a function $f(x, y)$ of the form:

$$y \cdot x^q = y_0 \cdot x_0^q, \quad q > 0 \tag{7}$$

Since $f(x, y)$ is continuous and monotone, then in any neighbourhood of the point (x_0, y_0) there exist $(x_1, y_1) \neq (x_0, y_0)$ such that $f(x_0, y_0) = f(x_1, y_1) = S$. Consider $a = \frac{x_1}{x_0}, b = \frac{y_1}{y_0}$, that is, $f(x_0, y_0) = f(a \cdot x_0, b \cdot y_0) = S$.

It follows from property (5) and lemma ?? that $f(a \cdot x_0, b \cdot y_0) = f(a^2 \cdot x_0, b^2 \cdot y_0)$, similarly, $f(a^n \cdot x_0, b^n \cdot y_0) = C \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Now we can show that:

$$f(a^t \cdot x_0, b^t \cdot y_0) = C \forall t \in \mathbb{R} \tag{8}$$

To prove it, we construct a convergent toward each intermediate degree sequence. Let us prove the equality for the middle point between any two points that are already checked:

Let $f(a^{0.5} \cdot x_0, b^{0.5} \cdot y_0) > f(x_0, y_0)$, then $f(a \cdot x_0, b \cdot y_0) > f(a^{0.5} \cdot x_0, b^{0.5} \cdot y_0) > f(x_0, y_0)$ is a contradiction, and a contradiction for the assumption $f(a^{0.5} \cdot x_0, b^{0.5} \cdot y_0) < f(x_0, y_0)$.

The expression of y in terms of t in x in the formula (7) gives:

$$y = \frac{y_0}{x_0^{\log_a(b)}} \cdot x^{\log_a(b)} \tag{9}$$

That is, an equipotential curve of the form (9) passes through any point (x_0, y_0) . Since $f(x, y)$ is strictly monotonic, it follows that $\log_a(b) < 0$. Denote $q = -\log_a(b)$, then the level line takes the form $y \cdot x^q = y_0 \cdot x_0^q, q > 0$.

2) Lets now prove that if there are two equipotential curves $y \cdot x^q = a$, $q > 0$, $y \cdot x^r = b$, $r > 0$, then $r = q$. Suppose that this is wrong, and lets try to find the intersection point of these curves. That is, we must find $\frac{x^q}{a} = \frac{x^r}{b}$. If $r \neq q$, then the solution exists: $x = \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{\frac{1}{q-r}}$. Thus, the specified equipotential curves correspond to the same value of $f(x, y)$. This also means that all points between these curves provide the same function value due to the monotonicity. We have obtained a contradiction with the strict monotonicity.

3) The statement that $f(x, y)$ is representable in the form $g(x^q \cdot y)$ means that if $x_1^q \cdot y_1 = x_2^q \cdot y_2$, then $f(x_1, y_1) = f(x_2, y_2)$.

From 1) and 2) it follows that through any point there passes an equipotential curve of the form $y \cdot x^r = y_0 \cdot x_0^r$, $r > 0$ with the same r for the whole definition domain. Consider the theorem statement for $q = r$. Since $x_1^q \cdot y_1 = x_2^q \cdot y_2$, they lie on the same equipotential curve, that is, $f(x_1, y_1) = f(x_2, y_2)$. \square

Lemma 3. *Suppose that $F(f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)) = g(f_1(x)^{j_1} \cdot f_2(x)^{j_2} \dots f_k(x)^{j_k})$ is a monotonically increasing function of k variables defined on the range of functions f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k , then $\min_{x \in X}(F(f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)))$ is attained at the minimum point $\min_{x \in X}(f_1(x)^{j_1} \cdot f_2(x)^{j_2} \dots f_k(x)^{j_k})$.*

It follows from Theorem 1, Lemma 3 and Lemma 2 that all solutions to the problem of minimizing both compilation time and execution time could be found as minima of the functional:

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \left(\sum_i \text{exe}(l^*(p_i)) \right)^r \times \left(\sum_i \text{comp}(l^*(p_i)) \right)^j \quad (10)$$

In the case of several applications, using (3), we obtain:

$$F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) = \text{geomean}_K \left(\sum_{ki} \text{exe}(l^*(p_{ki})) \right)^r \times \text{geomean}_K \left(\sum_{ki} \text{comp}(l^*(p_{ki})) \right)^j \quad (11)$$

where $\text{geomean}(x_1, \dots, x_K) = \sqrt[K]{\prod_K(x_k)}$

The selection of the coefficients r and j allows regulating the level of optimization by controlling the proportion between the acceptable slowdown of performance and simultaneous reduction of compilation time. In other words, by setting different values for functional parameters it is possible to receive compiler tuning of effective compilation levels O1, O2, O3, or more aggressive optimization. Figure 2 illustrates the calculated exact functional minima for the task 175.vpr. It could be seen that the minimum of the functional 11 with coefficients $r=7$ and $j=1$ coincides with the desired on Figure 1 point. Figure 2 also illustrates another minimum point calculated using different coefficients.

3.4 Minima of the quality functional and Pareto-minima

Through every point with positive coordinates an infinite number of different equipotential curves for the functionals from Theorem 1 pass. That is, curves of the form

$$x^q \cdot y = c, q > 0 \quad (12)$$

Similarly, for any positive value of c it is possible to construct infinite number of curves of this type. For clarity, several equipotential curves for the value 1 are constructed in Figure 3. And in Figure 4 the equipotential curves of various functionals that pass through the point $[x, y] = [2, 1]$ are constructed.

Since the functional is strictly positive, the minimum of one of them will be achieved at a given point $[x, y]$ if all the remaining points of the considered set lie on its equipotential

Figure 2: Pareto border and functional minima for compilation and execution times for a set of optimizing lines. The figure illustrates the optimization quality functional minima points for 175.vpr application from CINT spec2000 suite. Points "O2 line", "O3 line", "line 3" and "line 4" stand for using the indicated optimization line for optimizing all procedures in the application. "Whole application Pareto optimums" are the calculated Pareto optimums for the whole application execution and compilation times. The minima are calculated for functionals 11 with parameters set to $\langle r = 7, j = 1 \rangle$ and $\langle r = 1, j = 2 \rangle$.

Figure 3: Functions $y^p \bullet x = 1$, $x^p = 1$, $p = 2^k$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $p < 1000$

Figure 4: Functions $y^p \bullet x = c$, $p = 2^k$, $k \in \mathbf{N}$, $p < 1000$, $c = 2^p$

curve, on the right, or on top of it. When minimizing different functionals, different points can be found. That is, could be found different Pareto minima. However, by minimization of the constructed functional some points of the Pareto boundary cannot be computed. The following lemma describes the correspondence between Pareto minima and possible minima of functionals of the form (12).

Note: Figure5 illustrates the statements of the Lemma.

Lemma 4. 1) Through any two points of the Pareto boundary $[x_1, y_1]$ and $[x_2, y_2]$ a curve of the form (12) could be drawn, that is, $\exists c > 0, q > 0 : x_1^q \cdot y_1 = c, x_2^q \cdot y_2 = c$

2) For the sake of definiteness, suppose that 1) $x_1 < x_2, y_1 > y_2$, and the constructed curve is $g(x, y)$. And let $[x_3, y_3] : x_1 \leq x_3 \leq x_2, y_1 \geq y_3 \geq y_2$. Then, if $g(x_3, y_3) > g(x_1, y_1) = g(x_2, y_2)$, then the point $[x_3, y_3]$ can not be a minimum of a function of the form $f(x, y) = x^p \cdot y$ for no p .

3) Let the curves of the form (12) be drawn through every two points. That is, some functions $\{g_i(x, y)\}$ are associated with their values $\{c_i\}$ at these points. Then an arbitrary point $[x, y]$ of the Pareto boundary is a minimum of some function of the form $f(x, y) = x^p \cdot y$ if and only if $\forall x_1 < x_2, y_1 > y_2 : x_1 \leq x \leq x_2, y_1 \geq y \geq y_2$ holds $g_i(x, y) \leq c_i$ for the corresponding $[x_1, y_1], [x_2, y_2]$ of the function g_i .

Proof. 1) Let us compute $r : y_1 \cdot x_1^r = y_2 \cdot x_2^r$, that is, $r = \log_{\frac{x_1}{x_2}}(\frac{y_2}{y_1})$, since for the Pareto boundary is true $\{x_1 < x_2, y_1 > y_2\}$ or $\{x_1 < x_2, y_1 > y_2\}$, then $r > 0$

2) This inequality means that for some $p : x_1^p \cdot y_1 < x_3^p \cdot y_3$ and $x_2^p \cdot y_2 < x_3^p \cdot y_3$. Since $x_1 \leq x_3 \leq x_2$, the first comparison does not change its sign with increasing p , and the second whit it decreasing. That is, for any p one of the inequalities will be satisfied. Therefore, the function will not reach its minimum in $[x_3, y_3]$.

3) The first part of the last statement is proved in 2). Let us show that if 2) is wrong for any pair of points with respect to $[x, y]$, then there exists p such that a minimum is attained in it. First exclude all points in which the minimum is not attained for any p . In this set, there will be at least two points with minimum x and minimal y for $p \rightarrow \infty$ and for $p = 0$. Now consider two neighbor points of $[x, y]$ and construct a function corresponding to the curve passing through them from 1). Since 2) is fulfilled for these points, the value of the function at the remaining points of the set is not less than the value in them, therefore, from the fulfilment of 2) for $[x, y]$, a minimum at $[x, y]$ is achieved on the function of this curve. \square

Figure 5: Pareto minima as minima of the functionals (12)

3.5 Cumulative execution time, compilation time and code size metric

While the multiplicative functional derived in Theorem 1 naturally applies to characteristics that are to be minimized without strict lower bounds (such as execution and compilation time), code size presents a different practical scenario. In many real-world environments — embedded systems, boot loaders, or instruction cache-limited processors — there exists a hard upper bound on the acceptable code size. Exceeding this limit renders the compiled code unusable, regardless of its execution speed.

One could extend the multiplicative form to include code size as

$F = \text{geomean}(\text{exe})^r \times \text{geomean}(\text{comp})^j \times \text{geomean}(\text{size})^q$, which would preserve the scale-invariance and multiplicative properties proved earlier. However, this formulation treats size as a soft preference rather than a hard constraint.

To reflect practical requirements, we augment the soft preference with a barrier-type penalty that enforces the hard limit $SizeMax$. The full functional thus combines both effects:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & F(l^*(p_1), \dots, l^*(p_n)) \\
 &= \text{geomean}_K \left(\sum_{ki} \text{exe}(l^*(p_{ki})) \right)^r \times \\
 & \quad \text{geomean}_K \left(\sum_{ki} \text{comp}(l^*(p_{ki})) \right)^j \times \\
 & \quad \text{geomean}_K \left(\sum_{ki} \text{size}(l^*(p_{ki})) \right)^q \times \\
 & \quad \text{geomean}_K \left(\frac{1}{SizeMax - \min(\sum_{ki} \text{size}(l^*(p_{ki})), SizeMax - eps)} \right)^s
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Here eps is a small constant to prevent division by zero, and $SizeMax$ is the hard upper bound on total code size. The penalty term grows to infinity as the total size approaches $SizeMax$, strictly enforcing the constraint. The parameter $s \geq 0$ controls the strength of the barrier: setting $s = 0$ disables the hard constraint entirely, leaving only the soft preference size^q . The multiplicative form preserves invariance under changes of measurement units for all

components.

It is also worth noting that code size is often implicitly taken into account when controlling compilation time, as the work time of optimization phases typically depends linearly or quadratically on the size of the intermediate representation.

4 An example of the real application of the functional

The purpose of this section is to illustrate the behavior of the proposed functional on concrete data. The specific choice of the SPEC2000 benchmark suite and the Elbrus VLIW architecture is immaterial — any table of execution and compilation times would serve the same purpose. Synthetic data could be used equally well; we present real measurements only to demonstrate that the functional works in a real industrial setting.

It is impossible to illustrate constructed compilation quality application for optimizations tuning during whole compiler development. Instead we propose an experiment, in which the quality functional is used to select optimization lines for procedures of a benchmark suite. As the experimental base, CINT spec2000 CPU and CFP spec2000 CPU benchmark suites [30] were used. All measurement were done using Elbrus compiler for a VLIW architecture processor.

The scheme of the experiment is:

1. Select a set of optimization lines.
2. Measure the procedures compile and execution time when using selected lines for compilation.
3. Calculate a functional minimum for the collected data. That is, define the theoretical optimal compilation line for each procedure.
4. Compile all applications in a suite using optimal compilation line for each procedure.
5. Execute compiled applications.

It should be noted that the optimization line assignment is done right after interprocedural optimization phase. That is, interprocedural optimization is the same for all tested cases.

In this experiment we used the same optimization lines that were described in the Section 3.1.

To completely exclude the impact of procedures on each other, it is necessary to collect the execution times of the applications for all possible variants of assembling the procedures included in them. To fulfil this for n procedures and k optimization, n^k executions are required. This is technically not feasible in a reasonable amount of time. Therefore, the execution time statistic was collected for compiling all procedures of an application with only one optimization line at once.

The execution time of each procedure was measured using the Elbrus simple sampling profiler tool gprof. In this case the IP of executing instruction is collected at the regular time intervals. The compilation times for procedures were measured from the start of intraprocedural optimization using the internal utility in microseconds. Since the interprocedural part is not separable for procedures and is the same for different optimization sequences, in the corresponding functionals its time has been added to the sum of the procedures compilation times. That is, the obtained data is a table of size $n * k$ for execution times and $n * k$ for procedures compile time.

To find the minimum of the functional, the method of coordinate descent was used. To reduce the probability of falling into local wells, a shift in the random direction was made every few steps. In addition, we performed descents from all points at which one line is assigned to all procedures. In all cases, the result of the solution coincided and was achieved in no more than $3 * n$ steps.

Figure 6: Theoretical and actual change of the execution time.

The figure illustrates the performance increase comparing to O3 Elbrus optimization level when using the minimum point of the quality functional (11) with $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 7, 1 \rangle$ and $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 2, 1 \rangle$. Theoretical results represent the theoretical execution speed-up calculated from statistical tables. Real results represent the execution of applications compiled using theoretical optimum lines.

To perform the last part of the experiment, we developed and used a non-release compiler utility which allow assigning optimization lines to procedures right after interprocedural optimization phase.

Figures 6 and 7 show the result of functional (11) minimization with $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 7, 1 \rangle$ and $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 2, 1 \rangle$ using collected data. Both minima points show average performance increase: 15.29% for $\langle 7, 1 \rangle$ and 8.86% for $\langle 2, 1 \rangle$ (Figure 6). The calculated compilation speed increases by 106% and 143% respectively comparing to using only default O3 line (Figure 7). Both points could be useful for tuning, but for execution priority minimum for $\langle 7, 1 \rangle$ is of more interest as it corresponds to acceleration of almost all applications, so we used it for the last two steps of the experiment.

For point $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 7, 1 \rangle$ Figures 6 and 7 show real execution and full compilation results. In general, the results calculated from the tables and the results of the actual execution correspond to each other well, but the real execution acceleration was a little lower than theoretical results: 12.3%. Some researchers on iterative compilation note that the measured influence of the change in the compilation of the remaining application procedures turned out to be insignificant for considered one. But our analysis showed that the main reason for theoretical and actual speedup difference is the difference in the use of cache memory at various compilation of remaining procedures. Thus, data prefetching or speculative loading for one procedure leads to removing the data needed for another procedure from cache memory. As a result, we could choose O2 optimizing line for a hot procedure with loops just because some other procedure didn't use too much cache-memory in O2 compilation mode. This effect was most strongly manifested on application 189.lucas. The main execution acceleration of 179.art and 183.earthquake is due to cache optimization which is harmful on average. One of the 181.mcf procedures was accelerated by prefetching. Both 168.wupwise and 177.mesa were mainly accelerated due to excluding some code splitting and loop optimizations for several procedures.

There is also a little difference between theoretical and full compilation speedup. Compilation time that was used to find functional minimum point consists of interprocedural and intraprocedural optimization time. Besides that, compilation process includes frontend and backend phases (in case of Elbrus with no optimization left there). Which in sum for considered compiler takes about 6% of all compilation time. Those extra phases also depend on the optimizing line chosen due to different code they work with. But it is impossible to make cor-

Figure 7: Theoretical speed-up of compilation and full compilation speed-up using the minimum of the quality functional.

The figure illustrates the compilation speed-up comparing to O3 Elbrus optimization level when using the minimum point of the quality functionals (11) with $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 7, 1 \rangle$ and $\langle r, j \rangle = \langle 2, 1 \rangle$. Theoretical results represent the intraprocedural and interprocedural compilation speed-up calculated using tables. Real results represent the full applications compile time. 100% compilation time change means acceleration of compilation by 2 times, 200% - acceleration by 3 times etc.

respondence of this time to exact procedure, so this time wasn't added to training time. There is also a little measurement error, however, it is noticeable only on applications with very short full compilation time.

It should also be mentioned that along with the compilation speed-up, the average resulting code size also decreased by about 5%. This correlation arises because aggressive loop unrolling and code duplication, which increase compilation time, also tend to increase code size. Thus, selecting optimization lines that minimize the functional implicitly penalizes such aggressive transformations.

5 Conclusions

This paper considered the problem of constructing a multi-objective compilation quality criterion that best matches users' expectations from the compilation process. The key theoretical result is that, under natural assumptions (monotonicity and scale invariance), the optimal quality functional must be **multiplicative** in its components and must be evaluated on the **entire compilation task**, not as a sum of independent per-procedure optima.

Specifically, we proved that all multi-objective scalarizations preserving the ratio scale property reach their minima at points of multiplicative objective aggregation. Consequently, the compilation quality criterion for execution and compilation times takes the exact form of functional (11). For code size, which often faces hard upper bounds in practice, we augmented the multiplicative functional with a barrier-type penalty term that preserves the overall multiplicative structure.

The proposed functional is applicable both to a posteriori tuning and to a priori optimization decisions. The priority between compilation time, execution time, and code size is controlled by the functional parameters r , j , q , and s enabling smooth trade-offs for different compilation modes. We also described the subset of Pareto-minimum points reachable by functionals of the constructed form.

The main practical contributions of this work are:

- A general compilation criterion that establishes a unified importance ratio between mul-

tuple compilation characteristics for tuning a whole set of optimizations.

- A proof that additive per-procedure functionals do not reach the Pareto frontier for the whole application, while the proposed multiplicative functional does.
- An exact, parameterized formula for the compilation quality functional that allows explicit control of the trade-off between execution time, compilation time, and code size.

The obtained result is purely mathematical and provides a formal framework for multi-objective compiler optimization. This trade-off is particularly important for VLIW architectures, where complex static scheduling makes compilation time a significant factor. To demonstrate practical applicability, we implemented the proposed functional in the Elbrus compiler (a VLIW architecture) and illustrated its use for a posteriori selection of optimization sequences for procedures in the SPEC2000 benchmark suite. This implementation has been in industrial use for approximately six years, confirming the viability of the mathematical approach in a real-world production environment.

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